

Strategic Management Capabilities and Performance of County Government of Kakamega, Kenya

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Abstract: The purpose of this study was to examine the influence of strategic management capabilities on performance of county government of Kakamega. The study was guided by the following specific objective, to establish the influence of leadership capability on performance of county government of Kakamega, The study adopted the transformative theory and human capital theory. The study used a descriptive research design with a target population of 72 middle level management staff from all the departments in the county government of Kakamega. Since the target population was small then the study worked with entire population which is census. Data collection instrument were structured questionnaire. Both primary and secondary data were collected. The researcher self-dropped and picked the duly filled questionnaires. Piloting was done to test the validity and reliability of data collection instrument. Data was organised, coded, edited to bring a meaning. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were done. Multiple regression was used to test the significant levels of one variable over the other. Analysis of variance was also done. The study established a positive correlation between leadership capabilities on the performance of the county government of Kakamega, Kenya. The study concluded that technological capability, leadership capability, employee capability and financial capability affects performance of county government of Kakamega, Kenya. The study recommends that the county leadership requires cooperation, paying attention, influencing, being adaptive, and to have collaborative leadership as well as adopting new leadership styles in order to survive the turbulent and ever changing global business environment. The finding will be of significant to the researchers, academicians, stakeholders and to the entire economy as a whole.

Keywords: Leadership Capability, Strategic Management Capability, Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the world of competition and turbulent business environment, achieving operational performance in organizations is dependent on multiple factors which may be internal and external (Quinn & Hilmer, 2014). Burak (2013) observe that in the modern competitive business environment, organizations from one sector to another can utilize strategic resources in attaining long term and short term goals. Choosing a business strategy that exploits distinctive competencies and valuable resources not only promotes operational performance of firms but also influences sustainable competitiveness of firms (Mwangi, et al., 2021).

A competitive position is normally one of the elements that provide a competitive edge to a business over and above the competition that it faces. Possession of strategic capabilities enable a firm to directly improve its value offering to the market or customers in terms of products or services which are a result of possession of core competencies (Wanjiku, 2017). Core

competence describes an organization specific capability which helps it stand out from the rest in the industry. It is the asset that defines the essence of the firm's business in terms of core capabilities which make it possible for the firm to compete with other firms in the industry effectively.

Globally, firms in various sectors strive to achieve high competitive advantage for instance Google, Facebook, Twitter, Amazon and Yahoo are examples of firms headquartered in United States that operate in information technology sector that have used their unique strategic capabilities to achieve high competitive advantage (Marston, Li, Bandy, Opadhyay, Zhang & Ghalsasi, (2011). At the centre of the growth and rapid expansion of these firms are unique resources both financial and human resources, intellectual capabilities among other strategic capabilities (Mwangi, et al., 2021).

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Organizational performance is an organization's ability in its resources utilization to attain organizational goals in a way that is effective and efficient (Daft, 2010). Federico and Magdalena (2011) define performance as an organization's way of carrying its objectives into effect. Organizational performance measurement is viewed from two views: non-financial or financial. Non-financial performance has the following aspects: reputation, innovation, quality, satisfaction of employee and client satisfaction. And, financial performance dimensions range from organization's growth, market value to profitability.

Strategic management capabilities are described as a set of abilities that exist or can be created in organizations to facilitate long-term competitiveness (Owuor, 2018). Strategic management capabilities help organization in managing the future by putting focus on the requirement and needs of clients and manage problems and crises cropping up in the environment they operate in and differentiates between operational capabilities: techniques and common processes which can be imitated and learned (O'Regan and Ghobadian, 2014)..

Ngugi and Karina (2013) in Kenya avers that maintaining a competitive edge in an unpredictable business environment, organizations should reconsider adopting strategic management capabilities in order to survive. Subsequently, Kilui (2015) in Kenya ascertains that strategic management capabilities are considered to be a function of organizational efficiency and effectiveness. Despite variations in strategic management capabilities from one organization to another, strategic interventions such as technology, employee development and financial capability can facilitate organizational performance. Without a strategic management approaches, achieving organization excellence is unlikely in the dynamic business environment. As companies intend to expand their market share beyond local territories and maximize profits, rethinking on strategic management capabilities will not only facilitate organizational agility but also organizational efficiency and effectiveness (Kimani, 2013). Strategic management capability in this study will be evaluated in terms of technological capability, leadership capability, employee capability and financial capability. Leadership capability is regarded by Alam et al., (2011) as the ability of leaders to use their charisma or knowledge to influence workers towards organizational goals. Leadership capability is the ability of leaders to involve employees in decision making process, motivate, mentor, delegate duties and implement change with minimal resistance (Quinn & Hilmer, 2014). Alhadid and Abu (2015) describe employee capability as the ability of workers to perform their duties more diligently based on the skills, knowledge and personalities possessed. Organizations that promote employee capability are likely to effectively perform unlike the ones considering employee development as an expense.

Kakamega County is a county in the former Western Province of Kenya and borders Vihiga County to the South, Siaya County to the West, Bungoma and Trans Nzoia Counties to the North and Nandi and Uasin Gishu Counties to the East. CIDP Its capital and largest town is Kakamega. It has a population of 1,867,579 and an area of 3,033.8 km². County has an altitude range from 1,240 metres to 2,000 metres above sea level. Southern part of the county is hilly and made of granites which raises it 1950m above sea level. Nandi Escarpment is a key feature on the eastern border of the county with steep cliffs rising from 1700m to 2000m. The county is also endowed with a number of hills like Misango, Imanga, Eregi, Butieri, Sikhokhochole, Mawe Tatu, Lirhanda, Kiming'ini hills among others. The County Integrated Development Plan 2013-2018 borrows on past Kakamega District development plans. The plan had envisaged the development of more than six policies to help the County Government steer those operations that support the sectoral areas of the Strategic Plan. Therefore the study seeks to examine the influence of strategic management capabilities on county government performance.

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Despite the opportunities business globalization presents, the results of county governments have been unsatisfactory in terms of goals achievements (Adhiambo, 2018). According to a report by Pharmacy and Poisons Board (2018), an approximate of 53% of the county governments established in Kenya not only not performing effectively due to financial constraints but also due to inappropriate strategies adopted. In this regard, the current research seeks to determine how strategic management capabilities and county government's performance in the Kenyan context relate.

Owuor (2018) point out those changes in regulations, competition, high chances of failure, stagnation of county governments are some of the issues of concern that are attributed to underperformance of the counties. Like any other competitive enterprise, rethinking on strategic management capabilities will not only enable county government navigate in the turbulent business environment but also sustain their competitiveness (Njaaga, 2017). Despite extensive studies have been conducted by Owuor (2018), Adhiambo (2018), and Njaaga (2017), clearly there exist inadequate proof about the link between strategic management capabilities on organizational performance thus applicability of this research in the county governments in Kenya.

A study by Khan and Huda (2016) investigated how health care organizations' performance is impacted by strategic management and found that organizational performance and competition level are strongly and positively impacted by strategic management. However, in data collection, interviews were employed resulting to qualitative data in involving few participants hence creating an issue of findings which cannot represent the entire population. Kasera (2017) study examined how performance of Health Institutions in Nairobi County and strategic management capability related and established that a negative correlation between leadership capability and organizational performance. Therefore the study sought to establish the influence of leadership capability on performance of county government of Kakamega, Kenya.

2. LEADERSHIP CAPABILITY

The concept of performance, which can be considered the degree to which organizations reach success, can be briefly defined as the contributions made to the objectives of the organization (Bass, 1985). Organizational performance is the 'transformation of inputs into outputs by achieving certain outcomes. With regard to its content, performance informs about the relation between minimal and effective cost (economy), between effective cost and realized output (efficiency) and between output and achieved outcome (effectiveness)' (Chen, 2002, as cited in Karamat, 2013). Daft and Marcic (2009) define organizational performance as the measure of when and how an organization determines its own objectives. The way an organization performs to reach these objectives is a determinant of the important role of managers in their display of leadership behaviors (Bass, 1985). Strategically, leadership capability is, in essence, a way of thinking, feeling and subsequently behaving and acting. It's your ability to have a developed sense of who you are and what you want to achieve. It's your ability to set the vision and the example. It's your ability to inspire, engage, direct and teach others (Royston G. 2019). Although leadership is generally defined as the 'art of ensuring others have the desire to strive to reach the common aims' (Kouzes & Posner, 1995), leadership cannot be considered successful and is of no importance in the context of the organization if the results obtained are not congruent with the common aims (Koech & Namusonge, 2012). Leadership is the most important driving force to increase the performance of the organization (Karamat, 2013). In addition, Furnham (2002) maintains that leadership is the effectiveness attained by means of reaching the organizational outputs and objectives, which are indicators for the quality of the leadership. Ullah, Ullah and Durrani (2011) state that leadership is related to the performance of employees and the participation of employees is important for organizational development.

According to Obiwuru, Okwu, Akpa, and Nwankwere (2011), one of the reasons why there is a relationship between leadership style/approach and organizational performance is that it necessitates innovation-oriented competitiveness within today's concentrated and dynamic market and the creative destruction of reduced profit and competencies (Santora, Seaton, & Sarros, 1999). Studies suggest that, in the face of such challenges, effective leadership can facilitate performance development (McGrath & MacMillan, 2000). In addition, to understand the effects of leadership on performance, it is important that leadership play a key role in developing the performance of the organization (Obiwuru et al., 2011). The improvement

of organizational performance requires the development of management, and a sustainable competitive advantage requires leadership (Avolio, 1999; Rowe, 2001). In this light, the holistic review of studies on the effect of leadership on performance is important to be able to show the nature of the relationship between the two variables. This study examined the effect of leadership on organizational performance. Furthermore, the moderators that were expected to moderate the effect sizes found in this study were identified as: (1) the leadership style/approach considered in the research, (2) the sample group/sector of the research studies, (3) the study's publication type, and (4) the study's publication year. Nowadays, businesses are decreasing the size of their hierarchies and redesigning their structures. Based on observation of leaders in administrative posts and other higher-level functions, researchers discovered that borderless, networked organizations need new manners of management with increased connectivity, or what is named "meta-leadership". Meta-leaders aim to accomplish outcomes that cannot be realized by one company or one function. Individuals working in diverse positions in the hierarchy need collaboration (Marcus, Dorn, Ashkenazi, Henderson, & McNulty, 2009).

Also, leaders must be prepared and enthusiastic. Carucci (2015) examined thousands of leaders who were promoted into leading positions to detect the most significant mistakes of leaders in such situations. The study found that credibility is not gained through perfection, as leaders gain credibility when they honestly share that the positions and jobs inside the organization are not proportional and are reflected in the bonuses, allocation of resources, and chances of promotion. Another study looked at another personal habit - sleep – and its effect on leadership. (Van Dam and van der Helm, 2016) state that the lack of sleep will negatively influence the behaviors of leaders, while adequate control of sleep will lead to an advance of the efficiency and effectiveness of the entire organization as well as improved creativity, and decision-making. Leadership styles include "quiet leaders" who move patiently, cautiously, and incrementally and do the right thing for their businesses, people around them, and themselves. Quiet leaders see the world as it is, in order to prevent any surprises from diverse situations. They move patiently, with contingency plans, and are ready in both positive and negative situations and their actions are quick and wise. They consider the importance of trust and understand that breaking this trust can occur quickly. (Badaracco, 2002). Leadership is even related to exercising and having power on followers, and this will directly link leadership to the two styles of "Command-and-Control" or "Charismatic".

Nowadays, leadership requires cooperation, paying attention, influencing, and being adaptive, and all these characteristics comprise the collaborative leadership (De Meyer, 2009). This change is the result of many elements including globalization, divisions of the value chain, abundance of knowledge workers, increasing demands and challenges in the society, spreading of the sources of information and innovation, changes in organizational structures of multinationals, increased importance of risk management, in addition to advancements of information and communication technologies.

Collaborative leadership entails getting the right mentality, reducing operation charges, viewing beyond the boundaries of the company, developing harmony, and maintaining the capability to connect smoothly with others, and in managing contradictions. (Goman, 2015) found that many bad organizational behaviors damage this new collaborative leadership style, and they are the abundance of silos in the workplace and the waste of collective capacities. These behaviors will negatively impact profitability, reduce the motivation of people, decrease creativity, and make the workforce less productive, and less joyful. Collaborative leadership style was able to replace the command-and-control by trust and active presence. In this environment, the followers are encouraged to see themselves as individuals of value, seeking additional knowledge, and increasing their network, while being more creative in proposing creative ideas, and contributing in the success of the business (StudyCorgi 2022). (Ullah, 2011) stated that many factors have resulted into growing need of collaboratively leading, and these factors contain and are not limited to the following changes: globalization, increasing reliance on technology, in addition to the fierce competition. Collier, et al., (2021) states that introduction of many cultures of collaboration that were less hierarchically-based, and despite all the challenges, efforts, time, and risk of implementing collaboration, but the senior employees of the bank acknowledge it as highly beneficial.

Leadership consists of structured methods, and not magic as it focuses on a vision that aims to achieve results. It consists of autonomy with clear directions and goals. In sum, the articles further advance knowledge on how to resolve the challenges of strategic leadership (Simsek et al., 2015), and deliver sustainable organization outcomes (Collier & Evans, 2020).

According to (Feser, Mayol, and Sirinivasa, 2015), for performance, leadership is a necessity, like oxygen for breathing. Leadership is a primary driver for the growth of organizations. A leader must inspire the followers. Leaders must know and acknowledge individuals' way of thinking and give trust, interest, and knowledge about what they need and desire. Leaders will be a source of organizational efficiency, establishing a positive environment and limiting conflicts. The definition of

performance is usually related to the outcomes of the company, its profitability, as well as the extent to which it attains the goals, succeeds in the strategic and operational objectives, benefits the shareholders, supports the environment and the society and maintains a healthy and prosperous track of responsible business management practices (Kaplan, and Norton, 1992). Many internal and external factors affect organizational performance. The American Management Association offered a guideline “How to Build a High-Performance Organization” (Studyorgi. 2022). The main findings were that higher organizational performance is the outcome of retaining the right people with appropriate qualifications, expertise, and methods of thinking in addition to the continuous development and training of these workers. According to (Kaplan, and Norton, 1992), businesses are urged to adopt the latest performance measurements, practices and tools to succeed, be more effective in the long run, survive, develop, compete and attain their goals. Furthermore, when it comes to performance, several metrics are available, and the requirements should be intensely tested before choosing a metric.

Executives and managers are the first who should assess performance because they are responsible for making the daily decisions in addition to strategic and operational decisions; therefore they need a fair amount of clear, complete and correct data that will establish the foundation of business performance’s measurements. According to (Eckerson, 2009), the implementation of the correct performance measurements may profoundly interfere with the existing organizational culture and with the way of thinking of the managers and the employees. Therefore those behaviors must be altered. (Kaplan, and Norton, 1992) noticed many financial and non-financial metrics could measure that performance. These measurements include, but they are not limited to return on equity, market share, return on assets, Baldrige’s Criteria for Performance, balanced scorecard method of Harvard Business School, return on sales, the performance prism, traditional performance measurements, and Tobin’s Q and total shareholder return (Cooper, and Kaplan, 1991) found that adapting effective and successful measurement program is sometimes an expensive duty concerning the needed leadership, hard work, investments in human resources and financial investments.

Maintaining accurate figures and information will assist managers to be more efficient and more well-defined in the functions of the business because sometimes, decisions based on incorrect information are harmful and may harm the brands, even if they are well prepared and designed. This change requires the efforts of the company’s leaders and top managers that will steadily be the most trustful source of support and advises to build and promote critical sustainable values, practices, and business procedures (Bower, 1977). According to Samimi et al. (2020), the management team’s relationship greatly influences the organization’s success. If the culture inside this level of leadership is not based on transparency, trust, and united aim, the team members are not encouraged to share their opinions. Instead, they may withhold information, leading to the plans being underprepared. The idea of a shared leadership perspective outlined by Norzailan et al. (2016) is founded on the belief that one person does not possess the necessary skills to manage all aspects of a business. Samimi et al. (2020) support this ideology, stating that delegation of responsibilities and open conversations about potential issues is vital for strategic leadership.

3. METHOD

This study adopted a descriptive research design. The target population for the study was 72, comprised of all middle level management in Kakamega County, Kenya. Since the study population was small, the study worked with the entire population which is census. Data collection instrument was questionnaire and other information relevant to the study. Both primary and secondary data was collected. Piloting was done to test the validity and reliability of the data collection instrument. The data was reduced, organized, coded, edited, classified using a table and analysed to bring out the meaning under each of the factors. It was crosschecked and verified for errors, completeness and consistency. It was then coded, entered and analysed descriptively using IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SSPS 23). Pearson correlation analysis was used to test the relationship between variables in the study hypotheses. ANOVA, multiple linear regression analysis was adopted computed to determine the statistical relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variables.

4. DISCUSSION

The study sought to establish the influence of leadership capability on performance of county government of Kakamega, Kenya. The findings are presented in a five point Likerts scale where SA=strongly agree, A=agree, N=neutral, D=disagree, SD=strongly disagree and T=total. From table 4.1 below, the respondents were asked whether leadership requires cooperation, paying attention, influencing, and being adaptive, and all these characteristics comprise the collaborative

leadership as well as adopting new leadership styles in order to survive the turbulent global business environment and position their businesses in the best situation. The distribution of findings showed that 53.0 percent of the respondents strongly agreed, 41.0 percent of them agreed, only 5.0 percent of the respondents were neutral, none of the respondents disagreed or neither strongly disagreed. These findings implied that leadership requires cooperation, paying attention, influencing, and being adaptive, and all these characteristics comprise the collaborative leadership as well as adopting new leadership styles in order to survive the turbulent global business environment and position their businesses in the best situation.

The respondents were also asked whether leadership is the most important driving force to increase the performance of the organization in the face of such challenges, effective leadership can facilitate performance development. The distribution of the responses indicated that 46.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 43.0 percent of them agreed, and 6.0 percent of them were neutral, 4.0 percent of them disagreed while 1.0 percent of them strongly disagreed to the statement. These findings implied that majority agreed that leadership is the most important driving force to increase the performance of the organization in the face of such challenges, effective leadership can facilitate performance development.

The respondents were also asked whether the way an organization performs to reach these objectives is a determinant of the important role of managers in their display of leadership behaviors. The distribution of the responses indicated that 42.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 34.0 percent of them agreed, and 8.0 percent of them were neutral, 7.0 percent of them disagreed while 8.0 percent of them strongly disagreed to the statement. These findings implied that the way an organization performs to reach these objectives is a determinant of the important role of managers in their display of leadership behaviors.

The respondents were further asked whether leadership cannot be considered successful and is of no importance in the context of the organization if the results obtained are not congruent with the common aims. The distribution of the responses indicated that 32.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 38.0 percent of them agreed, 13.0 percent of them were neutral while 9.0 percent and 8.0 percent of them disagreed strongly and disagreed to the statement respectively. These findings implied that leadership cannot be considered successful and is of no importance in the context of the organization if the results obtained are not congruent with the common aims.

The respondents were further asked whether leadership play a key role in developing the performance of the organization. The distribution of the responses indicated that 42.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 30.0 percent of them agreed, 18.0 percent of them were neutral while 4.0 percent and 6.0 percent of them disagreed strongly and disagreed to the statement respectively. These findings implied that leadership play a key role in developing the performance of the organization.

The respondents were further asked whether effective leadership capabilities enables high performance. The distribution of the responses indicated that 25.0 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 35.0 percent of them agreed, 21.0 percent of them were neutral while 19.0 percent and 10.0 percent of them disagreed strongly and disagreed to the statement respectively. These findings implied that effective leadership capabilities enables high performance.

Table 4.1: Influence of Leadership Capability

Statements on Leadership Capability		SA	A	N	D	SD
Leadership requires cooperation, paying attention, influencing, and being adaptive, and all these characteristics comprise the collaborative leadership as well as adopting new leadership styles in order to survive the turbulent global business environment and position their businesses in the best situation	%	53.0	41.0	5.0	0.0	0.0
Leadership is the most important driving force to increase the performance of the organization in the face of such challenges, effective leadership can facilitate performance development	%	46.0	43.0	6.0	4.0	1.0

The way an organization performs to reach these objectives is a determinant of the important role of managers in their display of leadership behaviors	%	42.0	34.0	8.0	7.0	8.0
Leadership cannot be considered successful and is of no importance in the context of the organization if the results obtained are not congruent with the common aims	%	32.0	38.0	13.0	9.0	8.0
Leadership play a key role in developing the performance of the organization	%	42.0	30.0	18.0	4.0	6.0
Effective leadership capabilities enables high performance	%	25.0	35.0	21.0	19.0	10.0

4.1 Inferential Statistics

4.1.1 Pearson Correlation

The study sought to establish the strength of the relationship between independent and dependent variables of the study. Pearson correlation coefficient was computed at 95 percent confidence interval (error margin of 0.05). Table 4.2 illustrates the findings of the study.

Table 4.2: Correlation Matrix

		Performance of County Government
Leadership capability	Pearson Correlation	.852**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	65

As shown on Table 4.2 above, the p-value for leadership capability was found to be 0.000 which is less than the significant level of 0.05, ($p < 0.05$). The result indicated that Pearson Correlation coefficient (r-value) of 0.852, which represented a strong, positive relationship between leadership capability and performance of county government of Kakamega, Kenya.

4.1.2 Multiple Linear Regression

Multiple linear regressions were computed at 95 percent confidence interval (0.05 margin error) to show the multiple linear relationships between the independent and dependent variables of the study.

4.1.2.1 Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

Table 4.3 shows that the coefficient of correlation (R) is positive 0.623. This means that there is a positive correlation between strategic management capabilities and performance of county government of Kakamega, Kenya. The coefficient of determination (R Square) indicates that 38.5% of performance of county government of Kakamega, Kenya is influenced by strategic management practices. The adjusted R^2 however, indicates that 36.3% of performance of county government of Kakamega, Kenya is influenced by strategic management practices leaving 63.7% to be influenced by other factors that were not captured in this study.

Table 4.3: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.623 ^a	.385	.363	7.3362

a. Predictors: (Constant), Leadership Capability

4.1.2.2 Analysis of Variance

Table 4.4 shows the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The p-value is 0.000 which is < 0.05 indicates that the model is statistically significant in predicting how strategic management capabilities affects performance of county government of Kakamega, Kenya. The results also indicate that the independent variables are predictors of the dependent variable with an F test of 63.132.

Table 4.4: ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	683.232	1	106.654	63.132	.000 ^b
Residual	1640.030	64	20.442		
Total	2323.252	65			

4.1.2.3 Regression Coefficients

From the Coefficients table (Table 4.5) the regression model can be derived as follows:

$$Y = 38.212 + 0.521 X_1$$

The results in table 4.5 indicate that all the independent variables have a significant positive effect on performance of county government of Kakamega, Kenya. The influential variable is leadership capability with a coefficient of 0.521 (p-value=0.000). According to this model when all the independent variables values are zero, performance of county government of Kakamega, Kenya will have a score of 43.212.

Table 4.5: Regression Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	43.212	3.822		52.531	.000
Leadership capability	.521	.163	.365	3.461	.000

4.1.3 Hypothesis Testing

H₀₁: Leadership capability does not have a significant effect on performance of county government of Kakamega, Kenya.

From Table 4.5 above, leadership capability ($\beta = 0.521$) was found to be positively related to performance of county government of Kakamega, Kenya. From t-test analysis, the t -value was found to be 3.461 and the ρ -value 0.000. Statistically, this null hypothesis was rejected because $\rho < 0.05$. Thus, the study accepted the alternative hypothesis and it concluded that leadership capability affects performance of county government of Kakamega, Kenya.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings the study concluded the following as follows; Leadership capability ($\beta = 0.521$) was found to be positively related to performance of county government of Kakamega, Kenya. From t-test analysis, the t -value was found to be 3.461 and the ρ -value 0.000. Statistically, this null hypothesis was rejected because $\rho < 0.05$. Thus, the study accepted the alternative hypothesis and it concluded that leadership capability affects performance of county government of Kakamega, Kenya. Based on the findings, the researcher recommended that the county government should have the capacity to expand and deploy the firm's core capabilities, and effectively combine the different streams of technologies to mobilize technological resources throughout the firms in order satisfy the customer needs in an efficient and effective ways. Leadership requires cooperation, paying attention, influencing, and being adaptive, and all these characteristics comprise the collaborative leadership as well as adopting new leadership styles in order to survive the turbulent global business environment and position their businesses in the best situation. They should also come up with ways of implementation of the firms' strategies as achieving desired financial outcomes requires the firm to accurately balance its expenditure and within the limitations of its income stream.

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